

Management

**A STUDY ON CAREER SATISFACTION OF ARTS AND SCIENCE
COLLEGE STUDENTS WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO
KANYAKUMARI DISTRICT**

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ABSTRACT

A Career is the sequence and variety of occupations (paid and Unpaid) which one undertakes throughout a life time. More broadly ‘Career’ includes life roles, leisure activities, learning and work. This study examines the Arts and Science college students’ career selections, career satisfactions, the influences of career guidance classes in career selection, students’ confident level about their selected career and factors determining the career selection. A Survey research design was adopted to obtain data from 100 respondents from various college arts and science students. The results of the study reveals that 68% of students are satisfied on their selected career, 82% of respondents are have confident on their selected career and career selection has been influenced by various factors such as job vacancy, goodwill, passion on career, status, society and own interest. The study concludes that career selection is the primary responsibility of students based on their won wishes. Career guidance classes can be offered to all school students to select suitable career according to the wish of students.

Keywords:

Career, career selection, career guidance class.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Career selection is one of many important choices students will make in determining future plans. This decision will impact them throughout their lives. The essence of who the student is will revolve around what the student wants to do with their life-long work. Every student carries the unique history of their past and this determines how they view the world. That history created, in part by the student’s environment, personality, and opportunity, will determine how students make career choices. It then follows that how the student perceives their environment, personality, and opportunity also will determine the career choices students make.

FACTORS IN CAREER CHOICE

The first factor in career choice, environment may influence the career students choose. For example, students who have lived on an island may choose a career dealing with the water, or they may choose to leave the island behind, never to have anything to do with water again. Maybe someone in the student's life has made a significant impact or impression, leading to a definite career choice. Parents' educational background may influence student views on whether or not to continue their education. Someone they saw on television may have influenced the student, or parents may have demanded that they assume a family business. These are various environmental factors that would lead a student to a chosen career.

How students have seen themselves in a role in which personality is a determining factor may influence a chosen career. Some careers demand that you have the personality to match the qualities of the occupation. A student's personality must be a self-motivated type, as to investigate career possibilities from early on in their lives, and not the procrastinating type that waits until they are compelled to decide. Students must take seriously the role grades play in limiting opportunities in the future.

Opportunity is the third factor that has shaped career choices for students. Opportunity may influence how students have perceived their future in terms of the reasonable probability of a future in particular career fields. The issue of poverty has played an important determining role in the opportunities available to all. The income level of high school families may determine what career a student chooses during a specific time in the student's life; choices that will determine a large part of that student's future. Some students will have to budget education according to their personal income.

2. OBJECTIVES

- 1) To find out the factor determining the career selection
- 2) To identify the students satisfaction level on their respective course
- 3) To investigate the influences of career guidance classes to choose the course
- 4) To analyze the students confident level about their career.

3. METHODOLOGY

COLLECTION OF DATA

The research has used random sampling to collect the data from 100 respondents who are studying in colleges at various disciplines and used structured questionnaire as a research instrument tool which consists of open ended questions, multiple choices questions and also used five point liker scale test in order to get data. Thus, questionnaire is the data collection instrument used in the study. All the questions in the questionnaire are organized in such a way that to relevant information that is needed for the study. Secondary data has been collected from various articles, journals projects and online resources.

TOOLS AND TECHNIQUES

The analysis of data in a general way involves a number of closely related operations, which are performed with the purpose of summarizing the collected data and organizing them in such a manner that they answer the research questions. In this research, the researcher used percentage method for data analysis and various pictorial representations such as graphs ,charts and diagrams used to interpret the data

ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION**1) Opinion about career guidance classes:**

S. No	Sources	No of respondents	% of respondents
1	Very useful	54	54
2	Useful	12	12
3	Neutral	8	8
4	Not useful	26	26
Total		100	100

Source: Primary data

This table and charts shows that career guidance classes help 76 % students to select their career. 26% respondents say that career guidance classes not influenced them to select their career.

2) Factors influencing college selection:

S. No	Source	No of respondents	% of respondents
1	By neighbor	12	12
2	Parents Decision	22	22
3	Own Decision	42	42
4	Others influence	24	24

Total	100	100
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Source: Primary data

The chart and tables shows that factors influenced while choosing college by students. 12% of respondents say that neighbors’ advises influenced the students to choose the college, 22% of respondents have chosen college according the wish of parents, 42% of respondents only choose their college according their own wish.

3) Reasons for selection of career:

S. No	Source	No of respondents	% of respondents
1	Job vacancy	40	40
2	Passion	19	19
3	Goodwill	32	32
4	Other	9	9
Total		100	100

Source: Primary Data

The above chart and table indicates that 40% of respondents have chosen their present career due to the existing job vacancies. 19% of respondents have passion on the selected career, the goodwill of career forced 32 % respondents to select their present career.

4) Satisfaction level of respondents on Selected Career:

S.No	Opinion	No of respondents	% of respondents
1	Highly Satisfied	28	28
2	Satisfied	40	40
3	Neutral	12	12
4	Not Satisfied	16	16
5	Highly not satisfied	4	4
Total		100	100

Source: Primary data

The above table and chart disclose that the satisfaction level of respondents on their selected career. 68 % of respondents are satisfied on their selected career, 20% of respondents are not satisfied on their selected career.

4. FINDINGS

- 38% of students are only selecting career according to their own interest and wish. 62% of students are selecting their career by the compulsion of parents, friends, relatives and neighbors.
- Career guidance classes help 76 % students to select their career. 24% respondents say that career guidance classes not influenced them to select their career.
- 12% of respondents say that neighbors' advises influenced the students to choose the college, 22% of respondents have chosen college according the wish of parents, and 42% of respondents only choose their college according their own wish.

- 40% of respondents have chosen their present career due to the existing job vacancies. 19% of respondents have passion on the selected career, the goodwill of career forced 32 % respondents to select their present career.
- 68 % of respondents are satisfied on their selected career, 20% of respondents are not satisfied on their selected career.
- 82% of respondents have confident to achieve their goal through selected career and 18 % of respondents not have confident on selected career.

5. SUGGESTIONS

- Allow the students to select their interested career and avoid the parents and others compulsion on selection of career.
- Provide career guidance classes to develop knowledge and awareness about career among students in schools and colleges.
- Government should take necessary steps to increase the enrollment of students in higher studies.
- Education institution should provide the good environment and opportunities to the students to increase the confident level on career.
- Education institutions should introduce various innovative courses according to the changing employment market.
- Education system to be modified and redesigned.

6. REFERENCES

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